

DEVELOPMENT OF FAULT TOLERANT ELECTRO-MECHANICAL ACTUATION SYSTEM FOR AILERONS OF REGIONAL AIRCRAFT

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KEYWORDS: EMA, aileron actuation system, fault tolerant, electro-mechanical actuation, more electric aircraft, power-by-wire, fly-by-wire

ABSTRACT:

During the last two decades, the aerospace industry has experienced a significant research boom in the field of actuation system for flight control surfaces which was historically the domain of hydraulic powered technology. The new trend, motivated by desire for cost reduction and satisfaction of environmental constraints (while maintaining current safety levels), naturally leads to a more electric aircraft (A/C) concept reflected on all of its systems. A first answer is Electro-Hydrostatic Actuation that removes the necessity of hydraulic power distribution with benefits in weight and overall installation constraints. A further development step is Electro-Mechanical Actuation (EMA) that completely removes dependency on hydraulics and is even more promising in terms of weight reduction.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. EMA application State of the Art

The usage of EMAs for flight control surfaces has been a subject of interest recently for many research and development centres [1] aiming for replacement of hydraulics to promote transition from fly-by-wire to power-by-wire systems of the A/C [2].

Nevertheless, electro-mechanical actuation systems are currently used predominantly for secondary control surface actuation (see Figure 1).

Application of EMAs in primary control surfaces is currently limited to military applications or as back-up actuators in commercial aerospace sector [3] due to insufficiently resolved main technical issues, e.g. safety, reliability, and fault tolerance [4]. This state persists despite of promising potential

advantages such as system complexity simplification, overall reduction of weight and CO₂ emissions, lower recurrent maintenance [5] etc.

Figure 1. Primary (in red) and secondary (in grey) flight control surfaces of a potential Regional Aircraft

New research projects in electro-mechanical actuation for A/C Flight Control Systems (FCS) are therefore addressing these topics.

1.2. Framework of the present research project

The Air Transport industry is facing big challenges trading between the evolution of the mobility requirements, the emerging of new business models, and the increasing pressure to reduce the environmental footprint of the sector. The entire aviation value chain needs to focus on the innovation of the processes, technologies and competences to deliver appropriate solutions while maintaining the remarkable levels of safety and security that characterize this sector.

Within the frame of Horizon 2020, European Aeronautical Research Programme Clean Sky 2 (CS2), as natural continuation of Clean Sky, is aimed at enabling cutting edge solutions for further gains in decreasing fuel burn and reducing CO₂, NO_x and noise emissions in Air Transport.

Advanced technologies, new architectures and configurations will be inserted and demonstrated, during CS2 Programme, at full system level to enable step-changes in environmental and economic performance. Thus, bringing crucial competitiveness advantage benefits to European Industry. Regional A/C is one of the Innovative Aircraft Demonstrator Platforms (IADPs) of CS2, whose goal is to integrate and validate advanced technologies to drastically de-risk their integration on future products.

Under Regional A/C IADP of CS2, Work Package (WP) 2 Technology Development, framework 2.4 Innovative FCS (see also Figure 2), a Call for Proposal was launched in 2016 by Leonardo A/C Division asking the Applicants to provide innovative technologies in order to develop an advanced (i.e. beyond the current state-of-the-art) Electro-mechanical Actuation Subsystem suitable for a primary flight control surface (i.e.: aileron) up to Technological Readiness Level (TRL) 5 (i.e. reaching subsystem integration and testing in Iron bird IROB) whose key features are:

- compact design to cope with typical installation constraints of a Regional A/C application;
- jam tolerant mechanism to mitigate this specific EMA risk;
- 2 EMA devices operating at the same time on the control surface.

Figure 2. CS2 Regional A/C IADP

The selected proposal was project TAIRA (Fault Tolerant Aileron Actuation System for Regional Aircraft) from Honeywell Technology Solutions, Czech Republic.

The main goal of project TAIRA is to resolve the above mentioned technological and environmental challenges by developing an innovative EMA based actuation subsystem. By successful demonstration, all the current technology gaps that prevent application of EMAs actuation on primary flight control surfaces will be significantly reduced or closed. This will enable highly competitive products with increased added value.

2. FCS SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture for the lateral control portion of a potential Regional A/C FCS within TAIRA project is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. FCS architecture for A/C lateral control

The Flight Control Electronics concept employs several redundancy management features, primarily focused around integrity and redundancy of control paths through multiple system elements.

The principal concept is to have:

- triplex redundant Flight Control Computers (FCCs), that collect and demodulate cockpit analogue signals coming from pilot and co-pilot inceptors (side sticks, trim commands and switches) and compute A/C Normal Control Laws in terms of aileron surface deflection commands transmitted to the actuation channels;
- triplex redundant Remote Interface Units (RIUs), acting as data concentrators of cockpit signals and serving as backup command path in reversionary control modes.

The FCS can generally operate in the following two modes:

- Normal Mode;
- Direct Mode.

In Normal Mode, the lateral control and stability control laws are executed within the FCCs to provide full system capabilities, including all performance enhancing functions like the Manoeuvre Load Alleviation (MLA) and Gust Load

Alleviation (GLA) [6]. In Direct Mode, that is a reversionary control mode entered when system failures prevent Normal Control Laws execution. The RIUs are used as interface between the actuation channels and the cockpit inceptors while FCCs are excluded; the Direct Control Laws are hosted within the Electronic Actuator Control Units (EACUs) and provide only basic open-loop stick-to-surface control with no enhanced performance functions.

The FCS modes of operation are determined by the EACUs based on the availability and validity of the input data and are shared within the whole actuation system.

3. AILERON ACTUATION SUBSYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

3.1. Actuation Unit

The aileron control surfaces of the Regional A/C within TAIRA project are positioned by electrically powered, electrically signalled actuators.

The actuation subsystem consists of four separate and independent actuation channels that control the position of two separate aileron flight control surfaces located on the trailing edge of the outboard wing sections. The actuation channel end effector is referred to as Actuation Unit (AU) and contains the actuator mechanical portion collocated with the power and control electronics creating single LRU. These AUs are located within the A/C wing structure close to leading edge of the controlled surface.

Each AU interfaces with a dedicated dual-lane EACU to receive the desired surface position command and engagement status. The EACUs communicate via digital buses upwards with FCCs and RIUs and compute the position and engagement command for their AUs based on the mode of operation and data received from FCCs and RIUs. A dual-lane EACU architecture (Command/Monitor, COM/MON) is selected to ensure integrity of the commands transmitted to the AU via independent command computation and cross-lane monitoring.

To support the A/C lateral control subsystem redundancy and to distribute the loads present on the control surface, each aileron surface is controlled by two actuation channels; the dual channel architecture is shown in Figure 4. Under normal conditions the channels operate in an Active/Active configuration allowing both actuators to move the surface. Under some failure conditions and during maintenance the aileron can operate in

an Active/Standby configuration. Health monitoring algorithms are implemented within the AU as well as in the EACUs to detect failures that can occur within the actuation channel and to isolate and disengage a malfunctioning actuation channel. The redundancy of the actuation channels allows for system operation with degraded performance under such failure conditions.

Figure 4. Aileron Actuation Subsystem Architecture

While in Active/Active configuration, the actuation channels support the aileron surface travel rates up to 60 degrees/second against loads up to 1500 Nm which enables effective implementation of the load alleviation functions. To limit the fatigue of local aircraft structures coming from possible force imbalance between the two AU controlling the same surface, a Force Fight Mitigation Algorithm is implemented in the EACUs that actively aligns the AU action when both actuation channels are Active.

3.2. EMA

Based on Honeywell analysis, there are two distinct approaches to the Fault Tolerant EMA design which are suitable for this application: either a system with controlled disconnect of a jammed actuator or utilizing redundant jam tolerant design [7].

The comparative sizing for both design variants, and other requirements, indicated that the redundant option provides much better performance in terms of weight, reliability, degraded stroke coverage and robustness with respect to environmental conditions.

Each aileron surface within TAIRA project will be operated by two such redundant EMAs in an Active/Active configuration. Each actuator contains two independent loadpaths in velocity summation configuration at the actuator's output. Displacement of the actuator's output rod is an average of each loadpath positions. The velocity summation mechanism provides inherent load sharing between the internal redundant paths. In case of jam of any single path within an actuator, the unaffected loadpath is still operable and the actuator output rod can be driven in degraded performance mode. In this specific application, it is more important that the actuator remains back-driveable on single-point jam event and thus the aileron is inherently protected from jamming without the need of any controlled action. Depending on the position in which the loadpath jammed the redundant EMA might not be able to cover entire stroke as in normal operation, but only a limited degraded stroke. The maximization of degraded stroke coverage was one of the main optimization objectives during the EMA design. Figure 5 depicts the degraded stroke as a function of jammed loadpath position.

Figure 5. Degraded stroke coverage

Even in case of jam in least favourable position (i.e. the limit one), the redundant EMA allows the aileron surface to be actuated by the unaffected AU significantly beyond neutral position. Even better degraded stroke coverage can be achieved by:

- life reduction of main components (roller- screw and bearings);
- increasing the overall EMA length (currently limited by the installation envelope longitudinal dimension).

The redundant EMA design consists of the following main units (see Figure 6):

- two Electrical Motors (EM);
- two reduction gear sets;
- two roller-screw assemblies;
- the velocity summation mechanism;
- an output rod, connected to the aileron lever arm;
- the housing components, that also carry the EMA reaction & kick link attachment points.

Figure 6. Redundant EMA internal architecture

The roller-screw assembly was selected over a ball-screw solution because of favourable load capacity versus screw assembly dimensions and weight ratio. This component also provides higher number of internal redundancies and when compared with ball-screws, roller-screws are also less prone to jamming as they are more shock tolerant and less sensitive to contamination. These desirable properties mostly outweigh a slightly lesser efficiency when compared with ball-screws. Roller-screw efficiency strongly depends on the helix angle and decreases rapidly with small screw lead. In order to preserve the back-drivability and adequate mechanical efficiency of the design, a roller-screw with sufficient screw lead was selected.

The roller-screws are powered by the EMs through the reduction gearboxes with a gear ratio optimized for the overall system mass.

The Motor Controller (MC) electronics is embedded in separate housing, as it can be seen in Figure 7. MC serves several purposes, namely controlling the two EMs to position the EMA output rod through which the aileron movement is controlled, reading and analysing data from sensors located inside the EMA mechanics and receiving commands from and reporting status to the EACU.

Figure 7. Actuation Unit – CAD render

The final design of AUs in their installation compartment can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Model of AUs' installation compartment

There are several different position sensors in the EMA assuring precise position control equivalent to up to 0.25 degrees of aileron movement resolution and supporting redundancy and dissimilarity as

required in respective avionics hardware standards. Sensors with high precision also provide inputs for health monitoring system for the prediction of mechanical malfunctions. Health monitoring data can be analysed during regular aircraft maintenance and actuators which show signs of unusual wear or risk of malfunction can be replaced to keep A/C safety at highest level while reducing A/C downtime.

As opposed to the EMA architecture, MC is designed with a fail-safe concept, utilizing a COM/MON architecture. This concept allows for entering a safe state after failure. A COM/MON architecture essentially contains two identical control blocks. The COM block is actively communicating with EACU and reading data from internal sensors and translates it into position commands that are further processed by two Digital Signal Controllers (DSC) (one for each EMA loadpath) paired with two motor inverters providing hi-voltage / hi-power signals for commutation of a pair of EMs. The MON block observes communication with the EACU and sensor readings initiated by COM and it executes the same control algorithms. Both COM and MON control blocks are running Continuous Built-in Tests (C-BIT) constantly monitoring system integrity.

C-BIT monitored faults:

- invalid EACU command;
- invalid MC response to EACU command;
- command timeout;
- erroneous reading from any of the sensors or their combination;
- error or timeout in the communication with DSCs;
- electric fault (inverter fault, power loss);
- jam detection.

If there is a fault detected in either COM or MON block, the MC is forced into passive state with motors disengaged providing only damping to the surface movement, while the surface remains controllable by the other actuation channel.

A very important aspect of MC design is to provide sufficient damping of the surface movement when both AUs are in Passive state to prevent occurrence of aileron surface flutter which may endanger structural integrity of the A/C.

4. SAFETY AND RELIABILITY

The safety assessment process principally follows guidelines of the ARP-4761. The initial set of safety objectives was derived from the Functional Hazard Assessment for Aileron Actuation Subsystem, as stated in Table 1 below:

Table 1. The summary of FCS hazards for the lateral control system

Description of Hazard	Failure Classification	Failure Probability Objective (per flight hour)
One aileron surface runaway, hardover, or oscillations	Catastrophic	< 5E-10
One aileron surface free floating	Catastrophic	< 5E-10
One aileron surface jammed	Hazardous	< 1E-07
Loss of all aileron function	Hazardous	< 1E-08
Loss of one aileron surface function	Major	< 1E-06

A Fault Tree Analysis has been performed at system level to determine how the individual failures or combinations of failures could result in the undesired events and to show decomposition of probabilistic objectives to individual elements of the Aileron Actuation Subsystem.

To ensure that the Aileron Actuation Subsystem provides sufficient mitigation from the aileron surface flutter, either due to disconnection of the control path or loss of the flutter damping in Passive state, each aileron surface must be controlled by two separated channels.

In addition, to provide mitigation to aileron surface runaway failure, both the EACU and the Motor Controller must utilize high integrity computational platforms.

The EACU utilizes a dual-lane COM/MON architecture to ensure high integrity of its output. The command lane of the EACU transmits the aileron surface position commands to the MC, while the monitor lane monitors the command lane outputs via data bus loopback reading and comparing the command lane commands with the internally calculated values. If an erroneous output command is detected by the monitor lane, the monitor lane has an authority to force the MC to Passive state.

Each EACU can support the Normal Mode and Direct Mode operation. In case FCCs cannot support Normal Mode operation or fail invalid, the EACU will revert its operation to the Direct Mode, thus only utilizing position commands from the RIUs.

The MC employs an architectural scheme and features like that utilized for the EACU. The

command lane of the MC receives commands from the EACU via digital bus. If the received position data are invalid, not received within defined time frame, or not accompanied by the valid Cyclic Redundancy Check, the MC considers data as invalid and forces AU to engage Passive state. The data validity monitor is hosted in both, the COM and MON parts of the MC.

The monitor lane of the MC hosts Command Response Monitor to prevent uncommanded movement of the aileron surface. The Command Response Monitor senses the position of the actuator output rod and compares the position with the internally calculated value. If the monitor detects fault, actuator motors are disconnected and the AU engages Passive state.

If a single loadpath of the actuator is jammed, the Command Response Monitor in the monitor lane will detect a fault and the actuator engages Passive state. However, the output rod movement is still possible while AU output rod is backdriven, with some restrictions on stroke.

5. VERIFICATION AND VALIDATION

Components of the system developed up to TRL 5 will be tested for relevant environmental conditions according to DO-160G standards.

Integration testing of the Aileron Actuation Subsystem developed within TAIRA project will be performed in two stages:

- on Actuator Test Bench (TB) designed by Honeywell, for verification and validation of requirements peculiar to the actuation subsystem;
- on Leonardo A/C Division IROB, for integration of the actuation subsystem performances within the A/C FCS.

5.1. Test bench (model-based design)

The TB is a testing device allowing to test the whole actuation subsystem in laboratory environment. It accommodates all parts of two actuation channels within its structure, provides their interconnection, allows to synchronously control EMAs and counter-load them by a hydraulic motor. In addition, the TB includes simulation of the stiffness and inertia of the flight control surface. An overview of the TB components is depicted in Figure 9.

Design of the TB allows testing in single channel as well as dual channel configurations (the latter with EMAs in Active/Active or Active/Standby dual channel configuration). The hydraulic motor is

disconnectable, as is the flight control surface inertia simulation mechanism, enabling testing of EMA or EMAs with or without the counter-loading effects. Single channel configuration serves mainly for functional and performance tests of the EMA whereas dual channel configuration enables testing of system advanced control features such as Force Fight Mitigation Algorithm.

Both stiffness and inertia simulator parameters are adjustable to enable harmonization with particular control surface characteristics. Whilst the inertia simulator can operate in both configurations, the stiffness simulation mechanism is inherently dedicated only for dual channel testing.

Figure 9. Actuator Test Bench

The TB enables testing of various EMA functional and performance characteristics:

- operating stroke in both direction;
- maximum rate at nominal load condition;
- stall load;
- position frequency response;
- static accuracy, hysteresis and resolution at no load condition;
- backlash;
- passive damping (static and dynamic);
- efficiency.

5.2. Iron Bird

Under Regional A/C IADP of CS2, WP 3 Demonstration, framework 3.4 Innovative on ground IROB (see also Figure 10), Leonardo A/C Division is developing a ground demonstrator of the technologies developed within the following frameworks of WP 2:

- WP2.3.4: Advanced Electrical Power Generation and Distribution System;
- WP2.3.2: Electrical Landing Gear;
- WP2.4: Innovative FCS (among others, the Aileron Actuation Subsystem from TAIRA project).

The IROB activities will be aimed at integrating and validating relevant technologies up to TRL 5.

Figure 10. CS2 Regional A/C IADP WP 3

Aileron Actuation Subsystem testing in IROB will be done in a dedicated test station (see Figure 11) and will be aimed at validating its performances (including MLA and GLA capabilities) and interfaces with the represented A/C flight control and power distribution systems.

Positive outcomes of IROB relevant activities will finally certify the maturity of the technologies developed within TAIRA project.

Figure 11. Aileron Test Station

6. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a design overview of an innovative fault tolerant electro-mechanical actuation subsystem for primary control surfaces, fully compliant with fly-by-wire and power-by-wire A/C systems and contains description of all system components including introduction to its verification and validation plan.

Key features incorporated on actuation subsystem level are the following:

- triplex redundant FCCs;
- triplex redundant RIUs;
- EMA jam tolerant mechanism, preventing jam of the output rod in case of jam occurrence within one of its load-paths;
- two channels in command/monitor configuration of the EACU, where the command channel is

- executing control algorithms, while monitor channel monitors command execution integrity;
- health monitoring algorithms ensuring that control electronics locks out malfunctioning loadpath if failure is detected and allowing system operation with degraded performance;
- concise overall dimensions and low power consumption at nominal travel rate 60 degrees/second under nominal load 1500 Nm.

In addition, the design enables the implementation of MLA and GLA systems.

6.1. State of the project

In the first half of 2019 the project TAIRA successfully passed Critical Design Review (CDR); afterwards the manufacturing phase of all its parts and subsystems has begun. Analyses, calculations and assumptions stated in the CDR documentation were supported by preliminary test results performed on functional prototypes of EMA and MC, confirming viability of the concept.

6.2. Next steps

After the conclusion of the manufacturing phase, there will be three subsequent steps of integration and testing of the Aileron Actuation Subsystem developed within TAIRA project:

- Honeywell in-house integration and testing phase (1st half of 2020);
- Leonardo A/C Division verification on TB (2nd half of 2020);
- Leonardo A/C Division validation on IROB (2021).

All these activities will allow the achievement of TRL 5 for the relevant technologies.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (CS2 JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 738180 between CS2 JU and Honeywell Technology Solutions [8].

Contractual obligations relevant to the dissemination activities are regulated by the above mentioned Grant Agreement. The confidential nature of the information exchanged and disseminated follows the Implementation

Agreement signed between Leonardo A/C Division and Honeywell Technology Solutions.

It is worth to note that the contents of this paper reflect only the authors' view and that the CS2 JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

8. REFERENCES

1. P. M. Churn, C. J. Maxwell, N. Schofield, D. Howe and D. J. Powell, "Electro-hydraulic actuation of primary flight control surfaces," *IEE Colloquium on All Electric Aircraft (Digest No. 1998/260)*, London, UK, 1998, pp. 3/1-3/5. doi: 10.1049/ic:19980341
2. C. Sciascera, P. Giangrande, C. Brunson, M. Galea and C. Gerada, "Optimal design of an electro-mechanical actuator for aerospace application," *IECON 2015 - 41st Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Yokohama, 2015, pp. 001903-001908. doi: 10.1109/IECON.2015.7392378
3. Aigner. B., Peter F., Stumpf E. et al., Assessment of electromechanical flight control actuators with regard to direct operating costs, Deutscher Luft und Raumfahrtkongress, DocumentID: 420171, Braunschweig, Germany, 16-15 September 2016
4. Qiao, G., Liu, G., Shi, Z., Wang, Y., Ma, S., & Lim, T. C. (2018). A review of electromechanical actuators for More/All Electric aircraft systems. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science, 232(22), 4128–4151.
5. Balaban, E., Saxena, A., Narasimhan, S., Roychoudhury, I., Goebel, K., & Koopmans, M. (2010, September). Airborne electro-mechanical actuator test stand for development of prognostic health management systems. In Annual conference of the prognostics and health management society 2010.
6. Thornton, Stephen. (2019). NASA-TM-4526 19940019822 Reduction of Structural Loads Using Maneuver Load Control on the Advanced Fighter Technology Integration (AFTI)/F-111 Mission Adaptive Wing.
7. J. C. Mare, *Aerospace Actuators 2: Signal-by-Wire and Power-by-Wire*, John Wiley & Sons, 2017, ISBN 9781119407195, 282 pages
8. Grant Agreement for Partners No 738180 TAIRA - H2020-CS2-CFP03-2016-01.